

CRITICAL THINKING AND SPEECH CULTURE

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Abstract: *This article is dedicated to problem of critical thinking and speech culture. Communicative competence is considered one of the main categories of speech culture, so it is important to know the basic communicative qualities of speech, such as accuracy, consistency, richness, diversity of speech, purity and expressiveness. Critical thinking abilities are closely related to speech components, namely normative, communicative and ethical.*

Key words: *culture, speech, critical, thinking, professional suitability, knowledge, the norms of the literary language, communication.*

The culture of speech is the ability to express your thoughts clearly and clearly, to speak competently, the ability not only to attract attention with your speech, but also to influence listeners, the possession of the culture of speech is a kind of characteristic of professional suitability for people of various professions: diplomats, lawyers, politicians, teachers of schools and universities, radio and television workers, managers, journalists.

The culture of speech is understood as: 1) knowledge of the norms of the literary language in its oral and written forms; 2) the ability to choose and organize language means that, in a certain communication situation, contribute to the achievement of communication objectives; 3) compliance with the ethics of communication.

Thus, the culture of speech contains three components: normative, communicative and ethical. The culture of speech presupposes, first of all, the correctness of speech, that is, compliance with the norms of the literary language, which are perceived by its native speakers as an "ideal", a model. The language norm is the central concept of language culture, and the normative aspect of speech culture is considered one of the most important.

However, the culture of speech cannot be reduced to a list of prohibitions and definitions of "right-wrong". The concept of "speech culture" is associated with the laws and peculiarities of language functioning, as well as with speech activity in all its diversity. It also includes the opportunity provided by the language system to find an adequate language form for expressing specific content in each real situation of speech communication.

The culture of speech develops skills of selection and use of language means in the process of speech communication, helps to form a conscious attitude to their use in speech practice in accordance with communicative tasks. The choice of language means necessary for this purpose is the basis of the communicative aspect of speech culture.

Communicative expediency is considered one of the main categories of the theory of speech culture, therefore it is important to know the basic communicative qualities of speech that have the best impact on the addressee, taking into account the specific situation and in accordance with the goals and objectives. These include: accuracy, consistency, richness and diversity of speech, its purity, expressiveness.

The ethical aspect of speech culture prescribes the knowledge and application of the rules of linguistic behavior in specific situations. Under the ethical standards of communication refers to speech etiquette (speech formulas greetings, requests, questions, thanks, greetings, etc.; to appeal to "you" and "you"; the choice of a full or abbreviated name, formula, treatment, etc.).

The use of speech etiquette is greatly influenced by extra-linguistic factors: the age of participants of the speech act (the purposeful actions of speech), their social status, the nature of the relationship between them (formal, informal, friendly, intimate), the time and place of communication, etc.

The ethical component of the culture of speech imposes a strict ban on profanity in the process of communication, condemns the conversation in "raised tones". The culture of communication is inherently connected with the formation and development of critical thinking skills, since critical thinking is a mental means of human activity.

Critical thinking is a widely used term that includes the skills of identifying, analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating information for making informed decisions [D.F. Halpern, 2001, p. 273].

The most adequate interpretation of the term critical thinking is presented by E.I. Fedotovskaya. According to the researcher, critical thinking is inherently connected with the reflection of students' activities, and includes the following characteristics of thinking [E.I. Fedotovskaya, 2005, p.180]:

- ❖ analytical thinking (analysis of information, selection of necessary facts, comparison and comparison of facts or events);
- ❖ associative thinking (establishing associations with previously acquired material, familiar facts, events; establishing associations with new features of the subject),
- ❖ logical thinking (the ability to logically justify proposed solutions to a specific problem and follow a logical sequence of actions when presenting solutions),

❖ systems of thinking (the ability to analyze the object of learning, the problem and its characteristics).

However, despite the different levels of critical thinking, university students should be able to identify problems in order to rationally synthesize and solve them. To solve the problems, recipients must fend off various hypotheses and offer appropriate conclusions based on indirect information, in the absence of the necessary knowledge or evidence. A hypothesis can be proven to be true if it is actually supported by the facts given, which is a much more objective proof of the true conclusion.

The logical framework for measuring critical thinking skills has defined critical thinking as a process consisting of three main parts. The first part is a problem-solving process in the context of interaction with the world and people in general. The second part is a process of reasoning based on basic knowledge and previously specified facts, conclusions drawn by induction, deduction and value judgment. The last part reveals the decision based on the understanding of the necessary information.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that critical thinking is defined as the ability and willingness of individuals to reflect on their own and others' thinking in relation to its truth, value and validity in a logical argument.

The ability to think critically, logically build the entire chain of events, creatively approach problem solving and decision-making, of course, are interrelated with the development of students' speech. The culture of speech, communicative expediency, ethical norms also depend on the ability to critically comprehend information. The communicative qualities of speech are formed through the construction of critical thinking skills, which inherently affects the ethical norms of communication.

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